

Effect of coating thickness and nano additive on permeability of some modified waterborne acrylic coatings

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Abstract : Durability and performance of polymeric coatings depend on barrier properties as well as parameters such as water absorption, chloride permeability, gases diffusion and water vapor transmission. It is necessary to determine the barrier properties in reference to permeation of moisture in polymeric coatings when exposed to high humidity conditions and rain. The purpose of this paper is to examine the effect of coating thickness and nano additive on permeability behaviour and water absorption. In the present study, acrylic coatings were modified with nano additive to study their effect on permeability behaviour and then compared with effect of coating thickness; and then the physico-chemical requirements for the coatings are characterized. The different coating thickness and effect of nano additives have been studied and discussed. This study on WVT and WVTR clearly demonstrated that the effect of adding nano additive is as good as having double coat of acrylic coating. This paper examines permeability with respect to coating thickness and nano additive for physico-chemical requirements necessary for coatings. Water vapour permeation through acrylic films can be controlled by the packing density of the films. Permeability studies of polymers will significantly improve the research and development of coatings. This study gives a direct correlation of effect of nano additive and coating thickness on permeation of coatings.

Keywords : Permeability, acrylic coatings, water vapour transmission, water absorption, nano additive.

Introduction

The protective coatings used in indoor/outdoor walls should fulfil different requirements such as improved mechanical, adhesion, optical, rheological, durability, and reduced water absorption and water vapour permeability. A negative effect on the concrete protection is caused by moisture which is the main carrier of penetration of aggressive ions from rain and water soluble gases such as CO₂ and SO₂ and hence corrosion and growth of microorganism takes place resulting in adhesion loss between the coating and substrate¹⁻³. As coating covers all surfaces, its water vapour transmission properties have to be known as the first step for evaluating substrate properties and the co-action between coating and plaster. Hence, it is necessary to determine the water vapour permeability to get the effectiveness of water borne coatings in concrete protection. Indeed, to keep up steady item quality and to grow new items, auxiliary portrayal, structural characterization and estimation of barrier properties of new coatings turn

out to be extremely pivotal. The performance of coatings is influenced by several factors such as surface treatment of inorganic or organic pigments, corrosion inhibiting additives, the morphology of particle, fillers, dispersing agents and nature of the binding material. Good barrier effects need good adhesion between the coating and the substrate. If good adhesion can be established, attack by water and other agents at the interface can be prevented⁴⁻⁶. Also permeation studies gave indication about the breathability of coatings which is an important issue with regard to thermal performance and indoor air quality of our buildings. In the context of breathability, vapour permeability is the rate of passage of water vapour through solid materials. Application of vapour impermeable coating to exterior surfaces can lead to moisture and efflorescence entrapment, potential spalling and delamination, as well as surface and coating degradation. By contrast, "breathable" coatings allow the diffusion of vaporous water through the surface treatment to the exterior environ-

ment⁷⁻⁹. In the past, conventional methods such as gloss and pull-off test, viscosity, salt-spray tests were used to determine optical, mechanical adhesion¹⁰⁻¹², rheological and ageing properties of the coatings respectively^{13,14}.

Strict pollution regulations and legislation in most of the countries have resulted in significant increase in production of waterborne coatings but are sensitive to humidity and hence their barrier properties with respect to permeation of moisture need to be determined. In a coating binder represents the matrix structure and its quantity relative to the pigments and fillers can significantly affect structure and hence the barrier property of the coating⁸. The most common method of formulating different coating compositions is using PVC. The Pigment Volume Concentration (PVC) is the ratio of volume of the pigments to the total volume of the solid components in the coating as shown in eq. (1). While the different densities of the components are taken into consideration in PVC, the volume contribution of air voids is not. Various reviewers found that the tensile strength of isolated pigmented films increased with pigment volume concentration as compared with that of an unpigmented film, reaching a maximum value at Critical Pigment Volume Concentration (CPVC). For values higher than the CPVC the tensile strength diminished. The ultimate strain was found to decrease continuously with the PVC. The reinforcing effect was more or less pronounced, depending on the binder/solids system involved, but in every case the changes in property were approximately proportional to the PVC¹⁵.

$$\text{PVC} = \frac{v_P}{v_P + v_B} = \frac{\frac{M_P}{\rho_P}}{\frac{M_P}{\rho_P} + \frac{M_B}{\rho_B}} \quad (1)$$

where v_P is the volume of pigment, v_B is the volume of binder, M_P is the mass of pigment, M_B is the mass of binder, ρ_P is the density of pigment, ρ_B is the density of binder.

Acrylic polymers and copolymers are widely used as a binder in many paint formulations mainly due to their good film forming and bonding properties. Acrylic coatings have also been used in conservation of cultural heritage as consolidants^{16,17} and/or protective coatings for wall paintings, statues, stones and porous materials^{18,19}.

These acts motivated us to study the waterborne acrylic based paints for protective coatings on interior and exterior walls of the buildings^{20,21}.

The consolidations of nano-sized inorganic particles into polymeric coatings offer the potential for enhancing a number of their properties, including consumption resistance, at generally low loadings. Lewis *et al.* has earlier reported that 3% (w/w) nano TiO₂ produced an optimum improvement in the corrosion resistance of acrylic coatings²². The size, shape and geometry of the pigment produce marked influence on the barrier properties of the coatings²³. Wu *et al.* studied addition of clay in acrylic resin and observed that clay act as impact modifier for acrylic coatings²⁴. The effect of the nanoclay content on the thermal decomposition of intercalated hybrid nanocomposites has been established by Nistor *et al.*²⁵. Mikleic studied effect of TiO₂ and ZnO nanoparticles on properties of waterborne polyacrylate coating and showed that nanoparticles reduced flow time and increased the colour stability²⁶. In present study, four different waterborne acrylic based coatings with different thickness and nano additive were studied. Water absorption and water vapour transmission of the coating films was measured and results showed that the barrier property of the waterborne acrylic based coating films against humidity decreased with decreased binder content due to uneven and possible irregular distribution of the pigments which resulted in porous coating films.

Experimental

Waterborne acrylic based coatings were prepared as usual using locally procured commercial aliphatic acrylic resin (30–40%), pigments/fillers (10–20%), mineral system (10–20%) and thixotropic agent (1–2%) and titania nano additives (5%). Titania nano additive was procured from Aldrich through local vendor and used as such. The pigment volume concentration of the coatings was kept at about 25% having compositions as shown in the Table 1. Common properties of formulated acrylic coatings are given below :

- Appearance : Milky white liquid
- System : Single component
- pH : 7.0–8.0

Table 1. Compositions of coating formulations

Coatings ^a	A	B	C	D	E	F
	30% Acrylic single coat	40% Acrylic single coat	Double coat of A	Double coat of B	A + 5% Nano additive ^b	B + 5% Nano additive ^b

^aPVC maintained between 40–50%.

^bTitania as nano additive is used which is a spherical metallic oxide particle of average size less than 100 nm.

- Coverage : 5–6 m²/L
- DFT : 150–200 μm for single coat
(Dry film thickness)

Coating film was prepared by casting the solution on a clean and smooth glass substrate using a paint brush and then allowed to dry at ambient temperature and pressure conditions. The films were easily removed from the glass substrate by immersing the samples in a beaker filled with water for a certain period of time. Coating films were dried at room temperature to remove residual water (IS 101)²⁷. Surface morphology of the coatings was observed using Scanning Electron Microscope (LEO, model 438 VP, UK).

Physical properties of the coating systems like drying time, coverage and film thickness are determined according to methods prescribed in ASTM D 1005-13 and D 1640-03 test methods^{28,29}. It can be noted that the panels were coated with a thickness as per standards so as to maintain the dry film thickness in the range of 150–200 μm. The touch dry time for different coatings varied from 3–5 h, while hard dry time varied between 24–30 h. The covering capacity of the coatings varies from 5.0–6.0 m²/L. Tensile strength and elongation was determined following the standard test procedures described in ASTM D 2370-02 using two Ton Shimadzu Universal Testing Machine (UTM, Japan). Bond strength was carried out as per BS 3900-07 using pull-out adhesion tester (Dyna Proceq, Switzerland)^{30–32}.

The most common test methods to measure water vapour transmission in literature are JIS L1099, ASTM E 96, ASTM D 1653-13, ISO 11092 and BS 7209. In this paper WVT was determined as per wet cup method of ASTM D 1653-13 because it is very easy to perform and involved the determination of the rate of water vapour transmission as water vapour passed through films of paint, varnish and other coating³¹. In this method, to evaluate

water resistance of coating films static immersion test was used which followed gravimetric method. Coating film samples were immersed in distilled water at ambient temperature and then the coating films were removed at specific interval of time, blotted with a piece of paper towel so that excess of water can be absorbed from the surface. Change in weight can be calculated by eq. (2) and expressed as a function of time.

$$E_{SW} = (W_e - W_0/W_0) \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

where E_{sw} is the water uptake ratio of the film, W_e is the weight of the film at different times, W_0 is the dry weight of the film.

We can calculate the water vapour transmission (WVT) from eq. (2) and water vapour transmission rate (WVTR) from eq. (3).

$$WVT = (G/t)/a, \text{ grams per m}^2 \text{ per 24 h} \quad (2)$$

$$WVTR = WVT/d, \text{ grams per m}^2 \text{ per 24 h per mm} \quad (3)$$

where G is weight change, t is the time during which G occurred, a is test area, m², d is thickness of coating film, mm.

Weight loss of permeability cups after placing in desiccators continuously for one week was taken. Physical and mechanical properties of the developed acrylic coatings are given in Tables 2 and 3. Water vapour permeation experiments are mainly conducted to determine the effect of binder content on the barrier property of the coating films.

Table 2. Physico-mechanical properties

Coatings	A	B	C	D	E	F
Properities						
Tensile strength (MPa)	15	19	18	23	20	20
Elongation (%)	5	8	6	10	10	10
Bond strength (MPa)	3.24	3.76	3.40	3.80	3.80	3.64

Fig. 1. Loss in weight of permeability cups.

Results and discussion

A complete understanding of the relative importance of coating thickness and nano additive on the permeability of coatings does not exist in literature even today. We know that most common inorganic pigments and fillers are impermeable, thus, moisture transportation mainly takes place in the binder material. Unprotected concrete easily allows water vapour to penetrate inside the structure through fine flaws or cracks which are formed during curing and drying after construction. Present study is an attempt in this direction to develop a correlation among thickness of coatings and nano additive with the permeability.

In the present study we found that as the binder content increases in the coating films it results in drastic decrease in permeabilities i.e. from 0.2 to 0.04 g/24 h/cm²/mm. This behaviour is explained by the formation of porous structure as the binder content is decreased as we go from 40% to 30%. Similarly SEM micrographs of coating formulations with nano additives show more compact and wide distribution of particles as compared to corresponding normal formulation coatings with single coat but less than the double coat. Also these are more compact with less surface porosity than normal coating formula-

Fig. 2. Coating A.

Fig. 3. Coating B.

Fig. 4. Coating C.

tions with single coat. SEM observations support the water vapour transmission rate values given in Table 3. SEM

Table 3. Water absorption (in grams)

Time	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5	Day 6	Day 7
Coating A	0.097	0.086	0.083	0.077	0.075	0.072	0.072
Coating B	0.088	0.075	0.073	0.071	0.068	0.056	0.056
Coating C	0.035	0.035	0.028	0.027	0.027	0.023	0.023
Coating D	0.035	0.034	0.024	0.019	0.012	0.012	0.012
Coating E	0.045	0.037	0.033	0.031	0.030	0.030	0.030
Coating F	0.043	0.031	0.021	0.019	0.016	0.016	0.016

Table 4. Water vapour transmission using wet permeability cup method

Coating ^a	Slope	WVT (g/24 h/cm ²)	Thickness (mm)	WVTR (g/24 h/cm ² /mm)
A	0.0828	8.603×10^{-3}	0.040	0.21506
B	0.0730	7.584×10^{-3}	0.041	0.18498
C	0.0298	3.096×10^{-3}	0.073	0.04241
D	0.0241	2.504×10^{-3}	0.063	0.03974
E	0.0350	3.636×10^{-3}	0.059	0.06163
F	0.0257	2.670×10^{-4}	0.046	0.05805

^aExposed area of coatings = 9.625 cm² and minimum of five samples each.

Fig. 5. Coating D.

Fig. 6. Coating E.

analysis has also shown that the structure of coating films changes from porous to dense one with increase in binder content. Furthermore at lower binder content, the concentration of pigments in the film is higher, which results in non-homogeneous distribution of the pigment and hence water vapour permeability of the coatings is lower. Different phases are marked in the SEM images as – 1 for acrylic resin, 2 for pigments and 3 for nano additive (Figs. 2–7).

Fig. 7. Coating F.

Conclusion

We have demonstrated that water vapour permeation through acrylic films is controlled by the packing density of the films. This is because acrylic films with high packing density form high OH groups on the pore, induce strong interaction between the OH groups and the permeating water vapour, and thus protect against the permeation of water vapour. Therefore, densified double coated films show superior water barrier properties to acrylic single coat films and WVT follow the order :

$$(A, B) < (C, D) < (E, F)$$

The results obtained shows that the best barrier property against water vapour is shown by 40% binder content containing coating samples. This study on WVT and WVTR clearly demonstrated that the effect of adding nano additive is as good as having double coat of acrylic coating. We hope that the results of this study will help in promoting the use of nano additives in protective coatings.

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References

1. M. Hulden and C. M. Hansen, *Progress in Organic Coatings*, 1985, **13**, 17.
DOI : 10.1016/0033-0655(85)80025-X.
2. Y. X. Zhao, P. F. Du and W. L. Jin, *Journal of Zhejiang University SCIENCE (A)*, 2010, **11**, 349.
DOI : 10.1631/jzus.A0900580.

3. F. Pacheco-Torgal and S. Jalali, *Construction and Building Materials*, 2011, **25**, 582.
DOI : 10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2010.07.009.
4. V. D. Athawale and S. C. Rathi, *Journal of Applied Polymer Sciences*, 1996, **59**, 1243.
DOI : 10.1002/(SICI)1097-4628(19960222)59:8<1243::AID-APP6>3.0.CO;2-C.
5. E. Almeida, D. Santos and J. Uruchurtu, *Progress in Organic Coatings*, 1999, **37**, 131.
DOI : [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0300-9440\(99\)00064-8](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0300-9440(99)00064-8).
6. L. K. Aggarwal, P. C. Thapliyal and N. Attrey, *New Building Materials in Construction World*, 2011, **12**, 25.
7. J. W. Kim, S. M. Lee, J. K. Hong, J. C. Lim, B. S. Kim, S. Park, S. M. Hong, H. K. Lee and J. M. Park, *Journal of Industrial Engineering Chemistry*, 2001, **7**, 380.
8. N. S. Sangaj and V. C. Malshe, *Progress in Organic Coatings*, 2004, **50**, 28.
DOI : 10.1016/j.porgcoat.2003.09.015.
9. W. H. Koo, S. H. Choi, H. K. Baik, S. M. Lee and S. J. Lee, *Electronic Materials Letters*, 2005, **1**, 107.
10. E. L. J. Goossens, A. J. J. van der Zanden, H. L. M. Wijen and W. H. van der Spoel, *Progress in Organic Coatings*, 2004, **48**, 270.
DOI : 10.1016/j.porgcoat.2003.10.008.
11. V. Guillaumin and D. Landolt, *Corrosion Science*, 2002, **44**, 179.
DOI : 10.1016/S0010-938X(01)00028-2.
12. B. D. Amo, L. Veleva, A. R. Di Sarli and C. I. Elsner, *Progress in Organic Coatings*, 2004, **50**, 179.
DOI : 10.1016/j.porgcoat.2004.02.003.
13. M. Delucchi, E. Miglio and G. Cerisola, *PCE*, 1999, **40**.
14. C. Le Pen, C. Lacabanne and N. Pebere, *Progress in Organic Coatings*, 2000, **39**, 167.
DOI : 10.1016/S0300-9440(00)00148-X.
15. A. Toussaint, *Progress in Organic Coatings*, 1974, **2**, 237.
DOI : 10.1016/0300-9440(74)80004-4.
16. S. A. Altinkaya, O. Topcuoglu, Y. Yurekli and D. Balkose, *Progress in Organic Coatings*, 2010, **69**, 417.
DOI : 10.1016/j.porgcoat.2010.08.005.
17. J. Válek, J. J. Hughes and P. J. M. Bartos, *Materials and Structures*, 2000, **33**, 194.
DOI : 10.1007/BF02479414.
18. A. Ruus, P. Peetsalu, E. Tohvri, T. Lepasaar, K. Kirtsi, H. Muoni, J. Resev, E. Tungel and T. Kabanen, *Agronomy Research*, 2011, 197.
DOI : 10.1007/s13593-011-0040-2.
19. S. P. Miranda, O. Garnica, V. L. Saghon and G. Cardinas, *Journal of Chilean Chemical Society*, 2004, **49**, 173.
DOI : 10.4067/S0717-97072004000200013.
20. N. Sharma, V. Singal and D. D'Melo, *Pigment and Resin Technology*, 2013, **42**, 45.
DOI : 10.1108/03699421331288751.
21. T. F. L. McKenna, B. Charleux, E. B. Lami, F. D'Agosto and M. Lansalot, *Journal of Coating Technology Research*, 2014, **2**, 1.
DOI : 10.1007/s11998-013-9554-7.
22. O. D. Lewis, G. W. Critchlow, G. D. Wilcox, A. deZeeuw and J. Sander, *Progress in Organic Coatings*, 2012, **73**, 88.
DOI : 10.1016/j.porgcoat.2011.09.004.
23. P. Thometzek, A. Ludwig, A. Karbach and K. Köhler, *Progress in Organic Coatings*, 1999, **36**, 201.
DOI : 10.1016/S0300-9440(99)00037-5.
24. G. Wu, F. Yang, Z. Tan, H. Ge and H. Zhang, *Iran Polym. J.*, 2012, **21**, 793.
25. M. T. Nistor and C. Vasile, *Iran Polym. J.*, 2013, **22**, 519.
DOI : 10.1007/s13726-013-0152-4.
26. J. Miklecic, S. L. Blagojevic, M. Petri and V. J. Rajkovic, *Progress in Organic Coatings*, 2015, **89**, 67.
DOI : 10.1016/j.porgcoat.2015.07.016
27. IS 101. Indian standard methods of sampling and test for paints, varnishes and related products. Part 1. Test on liquid paints. Sec. 3. Preparation of panels, 2001.
28. ASTM D 1005. Standard Test Method for Measurement of Dry-Film Thickness of Organic Coatings Using Micrometers, 2013.
29. ASTM D 1640. Standard Test Method for Drying, Curing, or Film Formation of Organic Coatings at Room Temperature, 2003.
30. ASTM D 2370. Standard test method for elongation and tensile strength of free films of paint, varnish, lacquer and related products with tensile testing properties, 2002.
31. BS EN ISO 4624 (BS 3900). British standard methods of test for paints. E-10. Pull off test for adhesion, 2007.
32. ASTM D 1653. Method of test for moisture vapour permeability of organic coating films, 2003.